

**PRINCIPLES OF IMPROVING THE TECHNOLOGY OF ACME-LINGUISTIC
COMPETENCE**

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Annotation: *At present, special attention is paid to scientific research aimed at continuous professional development of medical workers, training of medical workers with a scientific outlook and the ability to communicate fluently in English, improving technologies for developing psycholinguistic formulas for the relationship between the needs of medical professional education and public health and speech structures, as well as acmelinguistic competence.*

Key words: *principles, acmelinguistics, systematic approach, foreign language.*

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Introduction: The need to improve the linguistic transformation in all directions of the development of the language literacy of young personnel is noted in the regulatory documents of our country, which determine the priority tasks in improving language literacy, which led to “the improvement of educational standards, curricula and plans, textbooks, as well as the modernization of teacher education and creation of advanced foreign educational centers for training in certain foreign languages”.

Thus, the main features of acmelinguistics are recognized: the patterns of achieving an acme level by a person through language, speech activity. basic principles of acmelinguistics.

Main part: The first principle is a systematic approach to improving acmelinguistics in teaching foreign languages to students. It is assumed that the student is given an educational task, which he must consciously accept and strive for its implementation at each stage. For a teacher, this means that he must give the student a training program (for a semester, a year, until the end of training) with precise indications of grammatical topics, vocabulary volume, texts, training exercises, etc., as well as the deadlines for completing a given program. It is clearly explained what he should know and be able to do and how to achieve this (including on his own). The ultimate goal is to turn the object into the subject of learning, i.e. to instill the skills of creative self-learning, self-improvement, both in the language and in the future profession. It specifically establishes what you need to know and be able to do and how to achieve this (including on your own). The goal of all training should be traced, where the object becomes the subject of training, a specialist with the skills of creative self-learning, self-improvement, both in a foreign language and in the specialty itself.

The second principle of acmelinguistics is the orientation towards the acmegram. Acmeagramma is a striving for excellence within a given specialty. The basis of the acmeagram is self-discipline, autonomy and self-development, that is, qualities that are inherent in a mature personality.

The third principle of acmelinguistics is taking into account the psychophysiological capabilities of students. Here they mean the abilities of an individual: memory, attention, thinking, perception of information, types of higher nervous activity. When teaching, it is necessary to take into account the quality of these psychophysiological features in order to obtain the best result in teaching foreign languages and personal development.

The fourth principle of acmelinguistics is consistency. The introduction of language tools (vocabulary, grammar, phonetics, orthoepy) and types of speech activity (speaking, listening, writing, translation) consistently. For this, certain learning rules are applied: 1) from simple to complex; 2) the rule of frequency - the more often it occurs in the language, the more time and attention is paid; 3) relevance and priority - training takes place mainly on the basis of the language material or type of speech activity that is needed in a particular specialization (for example, for physicists - reading and translation, for translators - listening, speaking and simultaneous translation).

The fifth principle of acmelinguistics is following acme ethics. Education of spiritual and moral qualities in a future specialist through teaching a foreign language (text material, role-playing and business games, situational exercises, one's own attitude to phenomena in society, etc.). In general, acmelinguistics is one of the modern technologies for teaching foreign languages in a non-linguistic university. The basis of such training is the formation of an independent and creative specialist striving for self-learning and self-development, an autonomous personality capable of teaching other specialists. Acmelinguistics makes it possible to build a training program where each type of speech activity is provided in accordance with the real needs of a particular specialty. It also gives impetus to self-development and self-improvement, which leads to the achievement of peaks by graduates in professional, creative, spiritual and moral activities.

In the studies of linguists (B.N. Golovin, A.A. Murashov and others), the concept of "speech culture" is used in three meanings: a) signs and properties of speech, indicating its high communicative level; b) a set of knowledge, skills and abilities that ensure the appropriate and free use of the language for the purpose of communication; c) the area of linguistic knowledge about the culture of speech as a set of its communicative qualities. In this regard, the thought of A.A. Murashov is especially important, who believes that "the culture of speech proceeds from the requirements of normativity and the expediency of choosing language means, takes into account the specifics of the situation of communication to a lesser extent, almost does not refer to the personal characteristics of the interlocutors, studies communication as a set specific linguistic factors.

Conclusions: The study of a foreign language has been and remains an integral part of the educational process in a higher medical educational institution. An indication of the level of foreign language proficiency is included in the qualification characteristics of a graduate of a medical university. Fundamental in the study of a foreign language at the present stage are: the formation of practical knowledge of a foreign language as a second means of communication in the field of professional activity; development of future specialists' skills to work independently and speak a foreign language after the end of the course. A feature of a foreign language as an academic subject is its pronounced communicative nature.

Literature:

1. Lapkin M.M. Study of the psychological determinants of the success of medical students' education. -M., 2014.-17p.
2. Acmeology. Methodological and methodological problems / Ed. N.V. Kuzmina, A.M. Zimicheva. - St. Petersburg, 2000. - 249 p.
3. Murashov A.A. Culture of speech: Textbook. - 2nd ed., erased. - Moscow-Voronezh: RAO MPSI, 2004. - 575 p.
4. Rumyantseva L.N. Acmelinguistics. - Part 2: To the teacher about the student / Ed. acad. N.V. Kuzmina. - St. Petersburg, 2000. - 180 p.

